

SELFAQUASENS

SELFAQUASENS pursues boosting the knowledge and researchers capital exchange within and beyond EU in order to develop new integral water remediation, revalorization and sensing technologies.

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SELFAQUASENS

Zero-Toxic Water
via advanced treatments, separation and revalorization technologies